

ELECTRONIC AND DISTANCE LEARNING IN MEDICINE

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Abstract: *Informatization of society and the introduction of innovative approaches to the learning process have created conditions for conducting training courses using distance learning.*

Key words: *distance-learning, electronic, medicine*

What is meant by distance education? Distance learning is the interaction of a teacher and students with each other at a distance, reflecting all the components inherent in the educational process (goals, content, methods, and organizational forms, teaching aids) and implemented by specific means of Internet technologies or other means that provide for interactivity. Distance education has been widely used in advanced training courses, as well as in teaching disabled children.

The question of the application of this form of education in medical schools remains debatable. On the one hand, the advantages of distance education are the possibility of teaching a large number of students at once, facilitating the educational process, in the case of teaching disabled people, adaptability - learning using modern software and hardware makes e-education more efficient, and, as a rule, distance learning is cheaper than conventional education, first of all, by reducing the cost of travel, living in another city, reducing the cost of organizing the courses themselves.

Opponents of the use of distance education in medicine believe that the development of practical skills, which are the main component in the training of future medical workers, is impossible in this way. However, in our opinion, the use of this form of education in medical schools is not only possible, but necessary. Naturally, training a doctor in practical skills requires traditional face-to-face contact, but all theoretical training and decision-making exercises can take place remotely. In order to correctly allocate the learning time into distance and traditional "phases", a thorough revision of the curriculum is necessary. Also, distance learning is the ideal and most optimal form of postgraduate education and advanced training, as it helps to solve a number of problems that already graduates have, for example, due to different work shifts and duty schedules for trained doctors, different approaches to work and study. There is also the possibility of using distance learning technologies for students enrolled in full-time departments, for example, when mastering general theoretical

courses. Of course, it should be noted that medical education has its own characteristics associated with teacher-student, doctor-patient relationships. However, even in such cases, distance learning demonstrates its flexibility. The following types of distance learning are possible: without the presence of a teacher, in the case of mastering a theoretical course, with the partial presence of a teacher, during practical and laboratory classes.

So, with minimal human and technical resources, it becomes possible to organize distance courses in parallel with traditional teaching methods. The basis for the introduction of these technologies can serve as trial courses organized on the basis of individual departments of the educational institution itself, as well as at clinical departments based on medical institutions. At the same time, according to Koshelev I.A., the system of distance learning and advanced training of medical specialists should consist of the following components: conducting remote lectures, conducting seminars with in-depth study of previously read lecture material; practical classes on certain methods of diagnosis, treatment and surgical operations, as well as individual telemedicine consultations. However, at present, the issue of the shortage of teachers who could develop and implement distance courses remains acute. It is easy to imagine that this requires special training not only on technical issues, but also on methodological ones: for example, the course developer must correctly determine the sequence and ratio of the distance learning part and the traditional one. Of course, the teams of medical universities are taking measures to overcome the difficulties that arise.

Summing up, we can say with confidence that today all conditions have been created to ensure effective distance medical education and advanced training in various areas of diagnosis, treatment or surgical intervention. Most likely, in the near future we will be able to say that distance learning technologies have been successfully introduced into the educational process of many medical schools.

REFERENCES:

1. Марухно В.М. ДИСТАНЦИОННОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ В МЕДИЦИНЕ // Международный журнал экспериментального образования. – 2012. – № 4-2. – С. 154-156;
2. www.ziyonet.uz
3. <https://mymedic.uz/>